

Optimization Of The Gaussian Algorithm: Applied to Electrical Circuits

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Abstract - The use of algorithms for constructing matrices would be a way of optimizing the traditional way of forming matrices, using the Gaussian scaling method, the code created in Scilab, would be an improvement for the construction of complex and large serial matrices and calculations related to electric circuits.

KEYWORDS: Scilab, Optimization, Gauss, Escalation, Code.

1| INTRODUCTION

In electrical engineering, it is possible to find, perhaps, one of the most evident uses of linear systems, given that many scientific and engineering problems can take the form of a system of linear equations.

The Gaussian Elimination Method, developed by a German mathematician Carl Friedrich Gauss, revolutionized the way systems of linear equations and continues to play a central role in solving complex problems nowadays. Which also becomes a fundamental technique in solving and analyzing electrical circuits. By applying this method to a system of equations that describe a circuit, it is possible to determine values of electric currents, voltages, among other electrical quantities in a systematic and efficient way.

To solve these systems, several simplifications and substitutions can be used, but when an excessive number of equations are assumed, this task becomes completely unfeasible. However, when using the Gaussian elimination method with scientific software for numerical calculation (for example Scilab), engineers and professionals in the field can calculate very complex systems, avoiding manual calculations. By the end of this article, readers will have an understanding of Gaussian Elimination and its important role in solving complex linear systems, contributing to a strong knowledge base in mathematics and its interdisciplinary applications.

2 | GAUSSIAN ELIMINATION

2.1 | Algorithm Optimization

For simple circuits, it is sufficient to use relations, in series and parallel, to simplify circuits. Ohm's Law, in this case, can be used to find voltages and currents easily.

Larger and complex circuits, however, become a problem, as this method becomes inefficient

Taking the following exercise, carried out in Dr. Alexandre Maniçoba de Oliveira's classes, as a basis, one must calculate the currents i_1 , i_2 and i_3 and the voltages V_1 , V_2 and V_3 , using the values of input shown in TABLE 1.

IMAGE 1 – Representation of the electrical circuit.

TABLE 1 – Representation of input values, provided in the previous example.

E1	E2	E3	R1	R2	R3
10	5	20	10	10	10
10	10	10	10	5	20

Using loop analysis, a linear system is determined and consequently the formation of a matrix is created to perform the calculation of the requested variables.

$$\begin{cases} -10 + 10i_1 - 10i_2 + 5 = 0 \\ -5 + 10i_2 - 20 + 10i_3 = 0 \\ 1i_1 + 1i_2 + i_3 = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 10 & -10 & 0 \\ 0 & 10 & 10 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 5 \\ 25 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Solving this system manually becomes completely unfeasible, knowing that the main objective is to optimize time when solving this type of problem. Therefore, the use of software to carry out these calculations is essential.

To start calculating the electrical circuit or matrices, after determining the values to be calculated, the application of the code in the Scilab software, where the values to be calculated begin to be inserted:

```
clear; clc

E1 = input("Insira E1: ")
E2 = input("Insira E2: ")
E3 = input("Insira E3: ")
R1 = input("Insira R1: ")
R2 = input("Insira R2: ")
R3 = input("Insira R3: ")
```

IMAGE 2 – First part of the algorithm code on Scilab.

This stage of the code is where the matrix representation occurs, and will be displayed in the code as the values presented, where the matrix formed from the values inserted represents.

```
a = [R1, -R2, 0;
     0, R2, R3;
     1, 1, -1];

b = [E1-E2;
     E2+E3;
     0;]

n=length(b)
a=[a,b]
```

```
disp("Matriz", a)
```

IMAGE 3 – Second part of the algorithm code on Scilab.

Once the Algorithm Optimized, to create matrices from the equations and in this step it will calculate the values represented in the fields from E1 to R3.

```
for j=1:n-1
  for i=j+1:n
    mf=a(i,j)/a(j,j);
    a(i,:)=a(i,:)-mf*a(j,:);
  end
end
```

IMAGE 4 – Third part of the algorithm code on Scilab.

At the end of the application, current and voltage calculations will be carried out and these results will be displayed, as in the following example, thus concluding the matrix calculations.

```
disp("Solução: ")

for i=n:-1:1
  ax=sum(a(i,1:n).*x)
  x(i)=(a(i,n+1)-ax)/a(i,i)
  disp("x("+string(i)+")= "+string(x(i)))
  I1=x(1)
  I2=x(2)
  I3=x(3)
end

disp("V1 = ", R1*I1)
disp("V2 = ", R2*I2)
disp("V3 = ", R3*I3)
```

IMAGE 5 – Fourth part of the algorithm code on Scilab.

3 | NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

TABLE 2 – Representation of input values, provided in the previous example.

E1	E2	E3	R1	R2	R3
10	5	20	10	10	10
10	10	10	10	5	20

In TABLE 2, the results obtained through system calculations, without any assistance from software focused on this field.

TABLE 3 – Results representation.

i1	i2	i3	V1	V2	V3
1,16A	0,66A	1,83A	11,66V	6,66V	18,33V
0,28A	0,57A	0,85A	2,85 V	2,85V	17,14 V

Using the first line of input values as an example, the value insertion screen displayed by the algorithm is shown below and consequently, when typing the variables, it is displayed thus the resolution of the system requested.

Insira E1: 10	"Matriz"	"V1 = "
Insira E2: 5	10. -10. 0. 5. 0. 10. 10. 25. 1. 1. -1. 0.	11.666667
Insira E3: 20	"Solução: "	"V2 = "
Insira R1: 10	"x(3) = 1.8333333"	6.6666667
Insira R2: 10	"x(2) = 0.6666667"	"V3 = "
Insira R3: 10	"x(1) = 1.1666667"	18.333333

IMAGE 6 – Fifth part of the algorithm, that shows system's resolution.

The debate on the improvements achieved based on the Gaussian Elimination method using Scilab and algorithmic optimization provides great information about the effectiveness of this process in solving linear systems. Thus, proving the importance of Gaussian Elimination in situations where precision is crucial, such as in scientific and engineering applications. The values obtained in TABLE 2 represent the practical application of the method. With the essentiality of the analysis of electrical circuits, these concepts applied to areas of electrical engineering are essential. The results show circuit currents and voltages, providing easy-to-use information for power system design and analysis. When dealing with complex systems, it is very useful to use algorithmic optimization, which, together with the Scilab code, simplifies the resolution of such problems and mitigates errors.

4 | CONCLUSION

In summary, solving linear systems is an important task in the exact sciences and especially in engineering. Gaussian Elimination, also known as scaling, is an interesting technique for this task. However, as the system becomes more complex, optimization becomes more valuable. In this context,

the algorithms presented in the Scilab code provided provide an efficient way to construct, develop and solve matrices, making the process more malleable and accurate. Numerical and experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of this method in providing accurate currents and voltages to the analyzed system. Therefore, as the presented experimental results demonstrate, optimization using algorithms such as Scilab plays an important role in solving linear systems and improves accuracy and efficiency of the analysis.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HwotCPT4WTY>.
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